

Cross Domain Sentiment Analysis on E-Commerce Datasets using Machine Learning and Ensemble Learning Approaches

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Abstract

There is an enormous amount of data available on internet on online user reviews about products feedback. This data is priceless for industries and businesses to take forthcoming decisions and develop marketing strategies for upcoming products based on users' interest. By making an analysis on available users' review data, organizations can understand the market trend and provide better service that can significantly scale up the business. This analysis on users' sentiments is achieved through data mining approaches where a model is trained on any particular domain data source and used on the new data to predict polarity of user interest. In some instances, cross domain sentiment analysis is very useful when labeled reviews are not abundant for model training. Though, there exist some works which address the problem of cross domain sentiment analysis but still there is need of a comprehensive research on usability of machine learning (ML) algorithms in this field and efficiency evaluation of them in cross domain sentiment analysis. In this work, we use various ML algorithms and ensemble classifiers to test their efficient in classifying different domain datasets in training and testing phase. Also, we propose an efficiency approach for feature extraction to enhance the prediction accuracy. We experimented our proposed work using various ML and ensemble approaches and evaluate the experiment results on various parameters like F1-Score, precision, recall, accuracy, AUC and ROC.

Keywords: Sentiment analysis, cross domain, machine learning, ensemble learning, transfer learning

1. Introduction

Sentiment classification is an important task in natural language processing (NLP). It can be used to identify user preferences, applied in the recommendation system or public opinion analysis [1]. Sentiment classification task aims to recognize sentiment polarity of documents (positive or negative). A lot of sentiment classification researches in the past have focused on training and testing classification models within a specific domain [2]. Sentiment analysis is a domain-dependent process [3] because different domains express sentiments differently [4]. For instance, the word 'easy' in the Electronics domain is normally positive, but in the Books domain, it carries a negative sentiment. The easiest way to address this problem is thus, to prepare enough labelled datasets for each domain for training a classifier [5]. The disadvantage of this method is that it is costly to manually label sufficient samples in every possible domain of interest. Moreover, a domain dependent classifier also requires a large amount of labelled datasets in order to be accurate [6]. However, in practice, there still exists a huge amount of insufficiently labeled data, where the traditional methods are hard to be utilized.

In many situations, plentiful product reviews from one domain (source domain) exist in which the sentiment is labeled but the application requires product review prediction from different, but related, domains (target domains) where the sentiment is unlabeled. Transfer learning is a necessary technique to resolve the lack of labeled reviews in cross-domain product review sentiment classification [7]. For example, assume that the task is to build a book review classifier and that an insufficient number of labeled book reviews are available for training the classifier but that labeled electronics reviews are abundant. However, different domains have different

feature spaces and distributions. A better solution to resolve this issue is by considering resource-rich labelled data from other domains, and by designing a more robust sentiment classifier which can work across different domains [2]. This scenario is called the multi-domain or cross-domain sentiment analysis [8].

As per Katz et. al [9], the cross-domain sentiment analysis is beneficial when labelled datasets are difficult to obtain. To learn the emotion of the sentences from unlabeled data, cross-domain sentiment classification has been proposed as a promising direction. It uses effectual information in the source domain (with sufficient labeled data) to help sentiment classification in the target domain (with few or no labeled data). As it is crucial for reducing the reliance on the massive amount of labeled data and significant for domains which are lack of labels, much research attention has been attracted from both academia and industry [6]. Cross-domain sentiment classification aims to predict sentiment polarity on a target domain utilizing a classifier learned from a source domain. Due to the difference between domains, the accuracy of a trained classifier may be very low. In this work, our major contribution is the improved TF-IDF technique which is integrated with feature weight coefficient positioning method. Also, in the preprocessing, we check for typo errors to get better accuracy in training as well as testing. We focus on various machine learning methods to assess their efficiency in classification of sentiments from cross domain datasets using proposed mechanisms.

Rest of the article is organized as follows: section II presents a literature review study about recent single domain as well as cross domain sentiment classification techniques for e-commerce dataset, section III presents proposed sentiment analysis solution to improve the cross domain classification performance, section IV describes the experimental setup and comparative performance analysis, finally, section V ends with concluding remarks and future work direction.

2. Literature Survey

Sentiment classification (SC) is a basic task in NLP. The demand of sentiment analysis applications has increased drastically during last decade. As the performance of text classifiers heavily relies on the extracted features, early work on SC mostly focuses on designing useful features from text content [10] and sentiment lexicons [11].

While conversing about single domain sentiment classification there are huge set of works done in the past. For e.g., Das et. al [12] proposed a technique for text sentiment classification using term frequency- inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) along with Next Word Negation (NWN). They have also compared the performances of binary bag of words model, TF-IDF model and TF-IDF with ‘next word negation’ (TF-IDF-NWN) model for text classification. Their proposed model is then applied on three different text mining algorithms and then it was found that the Linear Support vector machine (LSVM) is the most appropriate to work with their proposed model.

Kim et al. [13] in 2019, proposed a co-training based SSL method that attempts to exploit various perspectives in terms of feature subsets for the same example. In their work, they proposed a multi-co-training (MCT) for improving the performance of document classification. In order to increase the variety of feature sets for classification, they transform a document using three document representation methods: term frequency–inverse document frequency (TF–IDF) based on the bag-of-words scheme, topic distribution based on latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA), and neural-network-based document embedding known as document to vector (Doc2Vec). The experimental results demonstrate that the proposed MCT remains robust to parameter changes and outperforms benchmark methods under various conditions.

A multi-domain or cross-domain sentiment analysis is normally performed when there are similarities in features between the two domains [6]. In a typical domain adaptation process, the sentiment knowledge from a domain with sufficient annotated data (i.e., source domain) is transferred to a new domain with limited, or no labelled data (i.e., target domain) [3]. Prior to the knowledge transfer, analysis of the similarity between the source domain, and the target domain must be performed so as to reduce the differences in the feature distributions between the domains [3].

Zola et. al [14] proposed a novel cross-source cross-domain sentiment classification, in which cross-domain labeled Web sources (Amazon and Tripadvisor) were used to train supervised learning models (including two deep learning algorithms) that were tested on typically non labeled social media reviews (Facebook and Twitter). They explored a three step methodology, in which distinct balanced training, text preprocessing and machine learning methods were tested, using two languages: English and Italian. The best results were achieved using undersampling training and a Convolutional Neural Network. Interesting cross-source classification performances were achieved, in particular when using Amazon and Tripadvisor reviews to train a model that is tested on Facebook data for both English and Italian.

Meng et. al [15] in their work proposed a transfer learning method based on the multi-layer convolutional neural network (CNN). Interestingly, they constructed a convolutional neural network model to extract features from the source domain and share the weights in the convolutional layer and the pooling layer between the source and target domain samples. Next, we fine-tune the weights in the last layer, named the fully connected layer, and transfer the models from the source domain to the target domain. Comparing with the classical transfer learning methods, the method proposed in this paper does not need to retrain the network for the target domain. The experimental evaluation of the cross-domain data set shows that the proposed method achieves a relatively good performance.

In literature, Term Frequency - Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) is commonly used to create feature vectors for such tasks. However, TF-IDF formulation does not utilize the class information available in supervised learning. For classification problems, if it is possible to identify terms that can strongly distinguish among classes, then more weight can be given to those terms during feature construction phase. This may result in improved classifier performance with the incorporation of extra class label related information. We propose enhanced TF-IDF method in the next proposed section along with other techniques that are used in the proposed work.

3. Proposed Model

This section is all about proposed solution for cross domain sentiment classification in an efficient way. We formulated the problem and described the solution in further sub sections.

3.1. Problem Statement

Our main goal in this work is to classify cross domain reviews using proposed mechanism and evaluate performance of the proposed work using various machine learning algorithms. The problem can be formulated as: Let, $R = \{r^1, r^2, \dots, r^N\}$ be a set of N reviews and $CL = \{1, 2, \dots, y\}$ be a set of y class labels. Given a set of mappings of the form $\{r^1, cl_1^1, \dots, cl_y^1\}$ where review $r^1 \in R$ and class label $cl_1^1, \dots, cl_y^1 \in CL$, our goal is to find applicable class for a new data r^{new} .

3.2. Preprocessing

Before working with the data we preprocessed and cleaned it by performing the below-mentioned steps in sequence.

(1) Acronym Expansion: Reviews are generally written with various acronyms. We used a modified version of the dictionary given in [16] by adding some extra terms ourselves. All the abbreviated words were replaced by the phrase/words given in the dictionary.

(2) Spelling Correction: There are lots of typo error in review text due to shortened English form and mistakes. We use *pySpellChecker* library to detect and correct typo errors.

(3) Removal of non-ASCII Characters: Another prevalent problem with review text is special characters and emoji. We search for and removed all emoji and non-ASCII characters by pattern matching.

(4) Case Folding: All review texts were converted to lower case after all the above mentioned processing was done.

(5) Stop-words and Punctuation Removal: After all the above mentioned steps were done we removed any word from the review text which is present in the *nlk.corpus.stopwords*.

(6) Special Character Removal: We removed characters like ‘#’, ‘@’ without removing the corresponding hashtags or user mentions. Also, we removed some other special words like “rt”, “via” and “amp” which are not stop-words but contains no value whatsoever.

3.3. Improved TF-IDF

In literature, where textual feature is used, most common technique used for feature representation is Term Frequency - Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF). Here we explain working of TF-IDF and proposed TF-IDF method.

3.3.1 Traditional TF-IDF

In TF-IDF feature representation, each document or review text is represented as a vector where the fields correspond to the terms in the vocabulary. The value stored in a field is the TF-IDF score of the corresponding term. The TF-IDF score is the product of the Term Frequency (TF) of the term in that document and the Inverse Document Frequency (IDF) of that term in the corpus. Mathematically, TF-IDF can be denoted by:

$$TF.IDF = tf(t, d) * \log\left(\frac{N}{df^t}\right) \quad (1)$$

Where $tf(t, d)$ is the no. of times term t occurred in document d . N is count of documents or reviews in the dataset and df^t is the no. of reviews in which term t occurs. TF captures the importance of the term in the document and is computed as an increasing function of the term’s frequency. On the other hand, IDF tries to measure how informative a term is in the corpus. The assumption commonly made here is, if a term is frequent in a corpus then it is not much informative, whereas terms that are rare are more informative and hence important. IDF is modeled as a decreasing function of the term’s document frequency. This feature construction strategy using $TF.IDF$ is often used to classify text documents - both short [17] and long [18]. Although the formula considers the word frequency and document frequency two factors at the same time, the formula itself seems a bit too simple and lacks good discrimination. It calculates the term weight based on the term frequency. It does not care about the position of a term in the text, its semantics and co-occurrence with other terms in a document.

3.3.2 Feature Weight Coefficient Positioning

A variety of feature weighting methods have been introduced, and DF is the simplest one, where the “single appearance” of a word is equivalent with “multiple appearances” [19]. It counts the number of documents in which a word occurs, and uses the value to represent the corresponding document. TF is another criterion that explores feature weighting in a different direction. It is based on the intuition that the term of multiple appearances is more important than that of a single appearance [20]. IDF in essence is a kind of weighted trying to suppress the noise, and simply think text frequency small words are more important, the words with high text frequency are useless. That for most of the text information is not completely correct. The simple structure of the IDF can’t make extracting keywords very effectively reflect important degree and the distribution of keywords, and make it unable to complete the weights adjustment function very well. Especially in the corpus of its kind this method has great disadvantages, and often some of the same text keywords are concealed [21]. Each feature is represented as a binary vector, wherein “0” denotes the absence of the feature (evict the feature), and “1” denotes the presence (keep the feature) [22].

Feature weighting is a process of assigning appropriate weight to individual features in accordance with their relevance to the given domains. Different positioning of words in the text has varied effect in its importance as it affects the context meaning. Therefore, this paper introduced tag weight coefficient to describe the location of the special word in the text information.

Assuming that s_t refers to the sum of term t in the total number of documents, t_i is the i^{th} time term t appears in the document, K_{t_i} is the position weight coefficient of word t_i , So the key

t place in all the documents and the weighted average i.e. position weight coefficient b_t can be computed as:

$$b_t = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{s_t} K_{t_i}}{s_t} \quad (2)$$

we introduce the word class weight coefficient P_t , to describe speech constituent of keyword. It rules that noun has a value of 2.5, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs have a value of 1, the other word classes are 0.

3.3.3 Improved TF-IDF based on Word Weight Calculation Method

While calculating the text word weight variable, we introduce the balance variable into the text vector, substitute $\sqrt[n]{TF}$ for TF , to eliminate the excessive influence of term frequency and reflect the balance of weight [23]. For the keywords of a text, according to the position information of the word, the speech elements of the word and the improved algorithm, introduce the word class weight coefficient P_t and the position weight coefficient b_t to the traditional $TF-IDF$ formula. Thus, we can get the overall description of an improved $\overline{TF-IDF}$ weighted formula as:

$$\overline{TF-IDF} = \sqrt[n]{tf(t, d)} * \log\left(\frac{N}{df^t}\right) * P_t * b_t \quad (3)$$

In the above formula, $n(n \geq 1)$ parameter is mainly used to adjust the influence of TF , when the n value is small, it tend to the words with high TF ; when the n is a high value, it tend to the words with low TF . Upon experimenting we found that the cubic root of TF effect is the best to get the weight vector of the keywords. According to the weight we sort all the keywords, and then choose the first M keywords to constitute a text vector space model to represent the document content.

3.4. Feature Selection using K-Best and Chi-Square

3.4.1. K-Best

The main advantages for using feature selection algorithms are the facts that it reduces the dimension of our data, it makes the training faster and it can improve accuracy by removing noisy features. As a consequence, feature selection can help us to avoid overfitting. The basic selection algorithm for selecting the k best features is presented below:

SelectFeat(d, c, k):

1. $V = \text{ExtractVocab}(d)$
2. $L = |\emptyset|$
3. $\forall t \in V$
4. do $A(t, c) = \text{ComputeFeatUtility}(d, t, c)$
5. append($L, \langle A(t, c), t \rangle$)
6. return *LargestValueFeat*(L, k)

For a given class c , we compute a utility measure $A(t, c)$ for each term of the vocabulary and select the k terms that have the highest value of $A(t, c)$. All other terms are discarded and not used in classification. Chi-square can be used here as a utility measure as $A(t, c) = \chi^2(t, c)$

3.4.2. Chi-Square

In sentiment analysis, Chi-Square i.e. χ^2 test is used as a feature selection technique. Chi-Square measures the relationship between feature and target variables. If the value is zero means that the variables are completely independent. If the variables have higher χ^2 , they are very closely related to each other. If the value is higher, then the feature is of higher importance. χ^2 is one of the most efficient feature selection techniques in sentiment analysis. It is calculated as:

$$\chi^2(t, c) = \frac{N(AD - BC)^2}{(A + C)(B + C)(A + B)(C + D)} \quad (5)$$

Where, N is the total number of documents, A is the count of t occurrences and c occurrences, B is the count of t occurrences without c , C is the count of c occurrences without t , D is the count of non-occurrences of t and c .

3.5. Classification

The features selected after applying these feature selection techniques are trained using machine learning classifiers. Logistic Regression (LR), Support Vector Machines with RBF (SVM-RBF), Decision Trees (DT), Support Vector Machines with Linear Kernels (SVM-L), Multinomial Naive Bayes (MNB) and K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) are the classifiers used for performing sentiment classification. Also Ensemble learning approach is used where Bagging technique resulted in better outcomes compared with alone ML techniques.

3.5.1. Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression [24] is a supervised classification model. The input of the model is the K -dimensional eigenvector of the sample and the output of the model is the probability of a positive or negative class. For a given dataset $T = \{(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)\}$, where $x_i \in R^n, y_i \in (0, 1)$, the model hypothetical function that the function is shown below:

$$h_{\theta}(x) = P(y = 1|x; \theta) = \sigma(\theta^T x + b) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\theta^T x + b)} \quad (6)$$

where θ represents the model parameter, i.e. the weight before each feature, b represents the bias, and σ represents the sigmoid function.

Cost Function to train LR is:

$$J(\theta) = \frac{-1}{m} \sum y \log h_{\theta}(x) + (1 - y) \log(1 - h_{\theta}(x)) \quad (7)$$

3.5.2. SVM

In the context of text classification, let x_1, x_2, \dots, x_l be training examples belonging to one class X , where X is a compact subset of R^N [25]. Then we can formulate a binary classifier as follows:

$$\min \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + \frac{1}{vl} \sum_{i=1}^l \zeta_i - p \quad (8)$$

Subject to:

$$(w \cdot \Phi(x_i)) \geq p - \zeta_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, l, \quad \zeta \geq 0 \quad (9)$$

If w and p solve this problem then the decision function is computed as:

$$f(x) = \text{sign}((w \cdot \Phi(x)) - p) \quad (10)$$

3.5.3. DT

The decision tree model [26] is a tree structure classification model. A decision tree consists of nodes and directed edges. There are two types of nodes: internal nodes and leaf nodes. Internal nodes represent a feature or attribute, and leaf nodes represent a class. Using a decision tree classification model, start from the root node, test a feature of the sample, and assign the sample to its children according to the test results. The sample is tested and assigned recursively until the leaf node is reached. Finally, the sample is assigned to the class of the leaf node. The main idea is creating a tree based on the attribute for categorized data points, but the main challenge of a decision tree is which attribute or feature could be in parents' level and which one should be in child level. To solve this problem, De Mántaras [27] introduced statistical modeling for feature selection in tree. For a training set containing p positive and n negative: For a training set containing p positive and n negative:

$$H\left(\frac{p}{n+p}, \frac{n}{n+p}\right) = -\left(\frac{p}{n+p} \log_2 \frac{p}{n+p}\right) - \left(\frac{n}{n+p} \log_2 \frac{n}{n+p}\right) \quad (11)$$

Choose attribute A with k distinct value, then divide the training set E into subsets of $\{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_k\}$. The expect entropy (EH) remain after trying attribute A (with branches $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$):

$$EH(A) = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{p_i + n_i}{p + n} H\left(\frac{p_i}{n_i + p_i}, \frac{n_i}{n_i + p_i}\right) \quad (12)$$

Information gain (I) or reduction in entropy for this attribute is:

$$A(I) = H\left(\frac{p}{n+p}, \frac{n}{n+p}\right) - EH(A) \quad (13)$$

Choose the attribute with largest information gain as parents' node.

3.5.4. MNB

If the number of documents n fit into k categories where $k \in \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k\}$ the predicted class as output is $c \in C$. The Naïve Bayes algorithm can be written as:

$$P(c|d) = \frac{P(c) \prod_{w \in d} P(w|c)^{n_{wd}}}{P(d)} \quad (14)$$

Where n_{wd} is denoted to the number of times word w occurs in document, and $P(w|c)$ is the probability of observing word w in given class c [28].

$P(w|c)$ is calculated as:

$$P(w|c) = \frac{1 + \sum_{d \in D_c} n_{wd}}{k + \sum_{w'} \sum_{d \in D_c} n_{w'd}} \quad (15)$$

3.5.5. KNN

K neighbors [29] are a basic classification and regression method. Given a training dataset, for the new input sample, find the K samples closest to the sample in the training dataset. Most of the k samples belong to which class, and these samples are classified as this class. For a given training dataset $T = \{(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)\}$, where x_i is the feature vector of the sample, $y_i \in \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k\}$ is a sample category. The category, $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$; the sample feature vector is x ; output y is the category to which the sample belongs:

$$y = \operatorname{argmax}_{c_j} \sum_{x_i \in N_k(x)} I(y_i = c_j), \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, K \quad (16)$$

Where I is the indicator function i.e. I is 1 when $y_i = c_j$, otherwise, $I = 0$.

3.5.6. Ensemble Learning (Bagging)

It is a bootstrap ensemble that creates subsets of data from the original data with replacement. Base Classifiers are trained on each of the data subsets and the individual predictions are combined to output the final prediction. Bagging helps in improving the performance of a weak classifier by training multiple weak classifiers on subsets of original data. A bootstrap generates a uniform sample from the training set. If N bootstrap samples B_1, B_2, \dots, B_N have been generated, then we have N classifiers (C) which C_i is built from each bootstrap sample B_i . Finally, our classifier C contain or generated from c_1, c_2, \dots, c_N whose output is the class predicted most often by its sub-classifiers, with ties broken arbitrarily [30]. Bagging technique can be represented as:

Input: training set S , inducer τ , integer N

1. **for** $i = 1$ **do**

2. $S' = \text{bootstrap sample from } S$ (17)

3. $C_i = \tau(S')$

4. **end for**

$$5. C^*(x) = \underset{y \in Y}{\arg \max} \sum_{i: C_i=y} 1$$

output: Classifier C^*

3.6. Performance Evaluation

The performance metrics used to evaluate the classification results are Precision, Recall, F-measure and Accuracy. Those metrics are computed based on the values of true positive (TP), false positive (FP), true negative (TN) and false negative (FN) assigned classes.

True Positive: These are the correctly predicted positive values which means that the value of actual class is yes and the value of predicted class is also yes.

True Negatives (TN): These are the correctly predicted negative values which means that the value of actual class is no and value of predicted class is also no.

False Positives (FP): When actual class is no and predicted class is yes.

False Negatives (FN): When actual class is yes but predicted class is no.

3.6.1. Precision

Precision is the ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to the total predicted positive observations. It is given by:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

3.6.2. Recall (Sensitivity)

Recall is the ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to the all observations in actual class. It is given by:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

3.6.3. F1 score

F1 Score is the weighted average of Precision and Recall. Therefore, this score takes both false positives and false negatives into account. It is given by:

$$F1\ Score = \frac{2 * (Recall * Precision)}{(Recall + Precision)}$$

3.6.4. Accuracy

Accuracy is the most intuitive performance measure and it is simply a ratio of correctly predicted observation to the total observations. It is given by:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + FN + TN}$$

4. Results and Discussion

In this section, we present experimental analysis to show the performance of proposed cross domain sentiment classification technique. The obtained performance is compared via different machine learning algorithms. Below given table shows the experimental parameters considered to measure the performance of proposed approach.

Table 1. Experimental Setup

Dataset	Amazon Reviews
No. of Datasets	4 Datasets (Books, Kitchen, DVD, Electronics)
Operating System	Windows 8.1 Pro
Processor	Intel i5-8400 7 th Gen
RAM	16GB
Programming	Python 3.7
API / Packages Used	Sklearn, nltk-3.4, numpy-1.17.3, genism-3.8.1, pyspellchecker-0.5.4

In the table 2 below, we demonstrate the efficiency of various ML and ensemble techniques, while training the model on books dataset and testing on DVD, electronics and kitchen dataset. By analyzing the F1 scores of the classifiers, it is found that performance of bagging LR technique is higher than any other techniques.

Table 2: F1, Precision and Recall Score of ML Algorithms when Trained on Books Dataset and Tested on DVD, Electronics and Kitchen Dataset

	B->D			B->E			B->K		
	F1-Score	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Precision	Recall
LR	0.76	0.8	0.73	0.69	0.65	0.73	0.73	0.75	0.71
SVM-RBF	0.76	0.8	0.72	0.68	0.66	0.7	0.72	0.73	0.72
DT	0.64	0.61	0.66	0.6	0.54	0.67	0.62	0.58	0.67
SVM-L	0.76	0.81	0.73	0.7	0.68	0.73	0.68	0.68	0.69
MNB	0.74	0.72	0.75	0.67	0.61	0.75	0.69	0.68	0.7
KNN	0.67	0.98	0.5	0.65	0.88	0.52	0.62	0.81	0.51
Bag-LR	0.77	0.86	0.7	0.73	0.79	0.68	0.74	0.78	0.7
Bag-SVM-RBF	0.77	0.81	0.74	0.72	0.73	0.7	0.72	0.72	0.72
Bag-DT	0.65	0.64	0.66	0.64	0.64	0.64	0.67	0.59	0.77
Bag-SVM-L	0.77	0.82	0.72	0.68	0.65	0.71	0.72	0.73	0.71
Bag-MNB	0.76	0.81	0.72	0.7	0.7	0.69	0.71	0.73	0.68
Bag-KNN	0.67	1	0.5	0.67	0.95	0.52	0.66	0.88	0.53

In the table 3 below, we demonstrate the efficiency of various ML and ensemble techniques, while training the model on DVD dataset and testing on books, electronics and kitchen dataset. By analyzing the F1 scores of the classifiers, it is found that performance of bagging SVM-L technique is higher than any other techniques.

Table 3: F1, Precision and Recall Score of ML Algorithms when Trained on DVD Dataset and Tested on Books, Electronics and Kitchen Dataset

	D->B			D->E			D->K		
	F1-Score	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Precision	Recall
LR	0.68	0.64	0.73	0.7	0.64	0.78	0.72	0.71	0.72
SVM-RBF	0.69	0.65	0.73	0.7	0.64	0.78	0.69	0.67	0.72
DT	0.67	0.72	0.62	0.63	0.71	0.57	0.65	0.73	0.59
SVM-L	0.68	0.66	0.7	0.7	0.62	0.79	0.69	0.66	0.72
MNB	0.68	0.64	0.73	0.66	0.57	0.77	0.68	0.63	0.75
KNN	0.68	0.97	0.52	0.66	0.86	0.53	0.64	0.85	0.51
Bag-LR	0.7	0.7	0.71	0.71	0.69	0.74	0.71	0.71	0.71
Bag-SVM-RBF	0.72	0.72	0.72	0.7	0.65	0.75	0.73	0.73	0.73
Bag-DT	0.71	0.8	0.63	0.66	0.67	0.66	0.65	0.72	0.59
Bag-SVM-L	0.72	0.7	0.73	0.71	0.63	0.81	0.73	0.71	0.74
Bag-MNB	0.72	0.76	0.69	0.68	0.6	0.78	0.71	0.7	0.72
Bag-KNN	0.68	0.94	0.53	0.67	0.9	0.53	0.63	0.85	0.5

In the table 4 below, we demonstrate the efficiency of various ML and ensemble techniques, while training the model on electronics dataset and testing on books, DVD and kitchen dataset. By analyzing the F1 scores of the classifiers, it is found that performance of bagging multinomial naive Bayes technique is higher than any other techniques.

Table 4: F1, Precision and Recall Score of ML Algorithms when Trained on Electronics Dataset and Tested on Books, DVD and Kitchen Dataset

	E->B			E->D			E->K		
	F1-Score	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Precision	Recall
LR	0.65	0.64	0.68	0.71	0.74	0.67	0.79	0.83	0.76
SVM-RBF	0.64	0.61	0.67	0.7	0.74	0.67	0.79	0.83	0.76
DT	0.58	0.56	0.59	0.61	0.59	0.64	0.67	0.72	0.63
SVM-L	0.65	0.64	0.66	0.74	0.8	0.69	0.79	0.84	0.75
MNB	0.66	0.66	0.66	0.72	0.8	0.66	0.79	0.87	0.73
KNN	0.61	0.65	0.58	0.67	0.81	0.57	0.7	0.77	0.65
Bag-LR	0.67	0.7	0.65	0.72	0.8	0.65	0.78	0.84	0.73
Bag-SVM-RBF	0.68	0.71	0.66	0.71	0.75	0.68	0.79	0.8	0.79
Bag-DT	0.6	0.55	0.65	0.6	0.57	0.64	0.77	0.78	0.76
Bag-SVM-L	0.67	0.69	0.65	0.73	0.82	0.66	0.8	0.83	0.77
Bag-MNB	0.7	0.81	0.62	0.74	0.88	0.65	0.81	0.9	0.73
Bag-KNN	0.66	0.76	0.58	0.68	0.84	0.57	0.74	0.83	0.66

In the table 5 below, we demonstrate the efficiency of various ML and ensemble techniques, while training the model on kitchen dataset and testing on books, DVD and electronics dataset. By analyzing the F1 scores of the classifiers, it is found that performance of SVM-L technique is higher than any other techniques.

Table 5: F1, Precision and Recall Score of ML Algorithms when Trained on Kitchen Dataset and Tested on Books, DVD and Electronics Dataset

	K->B			K->D			K->E		
	F1-Score	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Precision	Recall
LR	0.65	0.66	0.64	0.69	0.65	0.75	0.78	0.69	0.91
SVM-RBF	0.68	0.71	0.65	0.7	0.65	0.76	0.78	0.68	0.91
DT	0.61	0.59	0.63	0.64	0.64	0.64	0.66	0.67	0.65
SVM-L	0.7	0.78	0.64	0.7	0.66	0.75	0.81	0.76	0.87
MNB	0.69	0.73	0.64	0.7	0.64	0.76	0.73	0.61	0.9
KNN	0.63	0.77	0.53	0.64	0.65	0.62	0.71	0.67	0.75
Bag-LR	0.68	0.71	0.65	0.7	0.67	0.73	0.79	0.72	0.88
Bag-SVM-RBF	0.67	0.68	0.66	0.63	0.56	0.72	0.77	0.68	0.89
Bag-DT	0.59	0.58	0.6	0.62	0.57	0.67	0.73	0.69	0.77
Bag-SVM-L	0.68	0.73	0.64	0.67	0.63	0.71	0.82	0.78	0.88
Bag-MNB	0.7	0.78	0.64	0.71	0.69	0.74	0.77	0.69	0.87
Bag-KNN	0.65	0.81	0.55	0.68	0.73	0.64	0.71	0.64	0.79

Below table 6 presents the accuracy scores of various ML and ensemble techniques, while training and testing the model on books, DVD, kitchen and electronics dataset. The average classification accuracy is derived that shows Bagging SVM-L method outperforms other techniques to achieve highest accuracy.

Table 6: Accuracy Score of ML Algorithms when Trained and Tested on Books, DVD and Electronics Dataset

Accuracy Score													
	B->D	B->E	B->K	D->B	D->E	D->K	E->B	E->D	E->K	K->B	K->D	K->E	Average
LR	0.75	0.7	0.72	0.7	0.73	0.72	0.67	0.69	0.79	0.64	0.71	0.81	0.7191667
SVM-RBF	0.75	0.69	0.72	0.71	0.73	0.7	0.65	0.69	0.78	0.66	0.72	0.81	0.7175
DT	0.65	0.64	0.65	0.64	0.59	0.61	0.59	0.63	0.65	0.62	0.64	0.66	0.6308333

SVM-L	0.75	0.71	0.69	0.69	0.73	0.7	0.66	0.72	0.78	0.67	0.72	0.82	0.72
MNB	0.74	0.7	0.69	0.7	0.7	0.71	0.66	0.69	0.78	0.66	0.72	0.77	0.71
KNN	0.51	0.53	0.51	0.54	0.55	0.52	0.59	0.6	0.68	0.55	0.63	0.72	0.5775
Bag-LR	0.75	0.71	0.72	0.71	0.73	0.72	0.66	0.69	0.77	0.66	0.71	0.81	0.72
Bag-SVM-RBF	0.76	0.71	0.72	0.72	0.72	0.73	0.67	0.7	0.79	0.66	0.67	0.8	0.7208333
Bag-DT	0.66	0.64	0.71	0.67	0.66	0.61	0.63	0.62	0.77	0.6	0.65	0.74	0.6633333
Bag-SVM-L	0.75	0.69	0.72	0.73	0.74	0.73	0.66	0.7	0.79	0.66	0.69	0.83	0.7241667
Bag-MNB	0.75	0.69	0.7	0.71	0.72	0.72	0.66	0.7	0.79	0.67	0.72	0.8	0.7191667
Bag-KNN	0.5	0.54	0.55	0.56	0.55	0.5	0.61	0.6	0.7	0.57	0.66	0.73	0.5891667

Figure 1: Training Time Required by ML Algorithms

In the figure 1 and figure 2, comparison is done considering the training time and testing time taken of different algorithms. Training time of KNN is comparatively lower than peer algorithms while testing time wise, ensemble LR is the best. On an average it can be said that Bagging LR has fastest compute time compared to its peers.

Figure 2: Testing Time Required by ML Algorithms

Below figure 3 presents the accuracy scores of best 4 ML and ensemble techniques, while training and testing the model on books, DVD, kitchen and electronics dataset. It shows that almost all techniques achieve highest score when trained on kitchen dataset and tested on electronics dataset.

Figure 3: Accuracy Score of ML Algorithms having Avg. Score \geq 72%

Below figure 7 presents the average accuracy scores of various ML and ensemble techniques, while training and testing the model on all four dataset. The average classification accuracy of Bagging SVM-L method outperforms other techniques but average scores of Bagging SVM-L, LR, SVM-RBF performs quite close to it.

Figure 4: Average Accuracy Score of ML Algorithms on Cross Domain Dataset Training and Testing

Figure 5: AUC and ROC Curve for Cross Domain Classification Evaluation (Training-Kitchen / Testing-Electronics)

Above figure 5, shows AUC (area under the curve) score of various ML and ensemble approaches. Also, it demonstrates the ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristic) curve of algorithms to have clear insight. In the next section we conclude the paper with future work directions.

5. Conclusion

Cross-domain sentiment classification aims to predict sentiment polarity on a target domain utilizing a classifier learned from a source domain. Due to the difference between domains, the accuracy of a trained classifier may be very low. In this work, our major contribution is the improved TF-IDF technique which is integrated with feature weight coefficient positioning method. Also, in the preprocessing, we check for typo errors to get better accuracy in training as well as testing. We focus on various machine learning methods to assess their efficiency in classification of sentiments from cross domain datasets using proposed mechanisms. The performance of proposed approach is compared with existing techniques which shows a significant improvement in cross domain sentiment classification performance. Accuracy performance of ensemble SVM-L on proposed mechanism has gone up to 83% when trained on kitchen dataset and tested on electronics dataset. Recently some studies have suggested that attention networks can produce promising results in the field of cross domain sentiment analysis thus it can be experimented with the datasets used in this paper to compare its efficiency.

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